

Advanced Practice Nurses in Swiss Primary Care—A Ph.D. thesis
about role perception, role definition, and role implementation.

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Summary

The Swiss primary care sector is under constant pressure, caused by the shortage of general practitioners and the multimorbid and aging society. This raised the question of how to maintain reasonable, high-quality healthcare in the country. Advanced practice nurses are regarded as one innovative approach to address the challenges that arise in Swiss primary care. The new profession arose around 2000 in Switzerland but is to date predominantly found in inpatient care settings.

This thesis focuses on the integration of advanced practice nurses/nurse practitioners into Swiss primary care. We implemented three studies that addressed the multi-level subject of role perception, definition, and implementation in primary care settings. In our first study, we focused on exploring the perspective of Swiss Master of Nursing students on primary care as a potential future working place. In our second study, we aimed to develop a uniform job description for advanced practice nurses in Swiss general practitioner practices in collaboration with experts from the practice. In the third study, we examined the acceptability of a nurse practitioner workload measurement tool from interest groups in Canada.

The objective of this thesis is to facilitate and cultivate a more profound understanding and integration of the role and profession of advanced practice nurses/nurse practitioners in primary care.

Table of Abbreviations

APN	Advanced Practice Nurse
APN-CH	Swiss APN association
BUAS	Bern University of Applied Science
CNS	Clinical Nurse Specialist
DRG	Diagnose-Related Groups
ECTs	Credit Points
FOPH	Swiss Federal Office of Public Health
GesBG	Health Professions Act (Gesundheitsberufegesetz)
GP	General Practitioner
ICN	International Council of Nurses
KVG	Health Insurance Act (Krankenversicherungsgesetz)
NCDs	Noncommunicable diseases
NHS	National Health Service
NP	Nurse Practitioner
OBSAN	Swiss Health Observatory
PA	Physician Assistants
PRiMA	APN in primary care (Advanced Practice Nurse in der Primärversorgung)
Spitex	Swiss Home Care
TARMED	Tariff for outpatient medical services in Switzerland
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1: Introduction

1.1. Background

Countries worldwide are considering healthcare reforms due to the high incidence rates of communicable and especially noncommunicable diseases, the rising costs of healthcare, and the shortage of healthcare professionals. Communicable diseases are still the leading cause of death in low-income countries (World Health Organization, 2024). Noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) are particularly high in industrialized countries. Recent data from the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that over 1.8 million deaths per year are preventable deaths associated with NCDs in the WHO European Region (World Health Organization, 2025). The chronic and complex healthcare situations have a direct impact on the increasing healthcare costs in Europe (Hertie School of Governance, 2019). In the United States, the prognosis for 2026 indicates that healthcare costs are on the rise in the next year, primarily due to constant pressures from medical services and prescription drugs (PricewaterhouseCoopers, 2025). The shortage of healthcare professionals is a worldwide issue due to an increasing demand, insufficient training programs, and an aging workforce (Džakula et al., 2022). These issues emerge from a tightened situation for healthcare around the globe. Proposed solutions for the healthcare professional shortage are an increase in education programs, redesigning care models with new roles and technologies, and systemic change in the sector (Kern, 2023). In Europe, the two roles of Advanced Practice Nurses (APN) and Physician Assistants (PA) have been acknowledged in the past two decades as innovative solutions to the challenges of healthcare delivery (McKee et al., 2025; Unsworth et al., 2024). Both roles contribute to improving access to care and addressing workforce shortages (Dankers-de Mari et al., 2023). APNs follow the advanced practice approach, characterized by an extended scope of practice, high level of autonomy, and responsibility for complex decision-making (National Health Services England, 2025). This thesis focuses on APN as the profession is considered a promising and sustainable solution, according to the WHO and the International Council of Nurses (ICN) (Schober, 2025).

The profession of today's APNs emerged in the 1960s in North America. Before, there were limited healthcare services available in rural and remote areas in Canada and the United States (US) due to the shortage of general physicians (GPs). Nurses were stepping up by expanding their capacity and taking on responsibilities and tasks that are in the scope of the practice of GPs and physicians (Kaasalainen et al., 2010). The two main advanced practice roles emerged from this time: the Clinical Nurse Specialist (CNS) and the Nurse Practitioner (NP) (Kaasalainen et al., 2010).

The profession of APNs evolved over the past 65 years globally. In the US, Canada, and Australia, APNs are a fundamental part of the healthcare system today. The profession progressed to autonomous healthcare providers maintaining nursing and clinical care services. This includes regulated and standardized education programs, a national licensing process from the country, title protection, as well as national associations, a defined scope of practice, and activities with specialized training (Freund et al., 2015).

In Europe, the implementation of APNs differs strongly between the countries. Countries like the Netherlands or the United Kingdom (UK) have made great progress in implementing APNs in the healthcare system and supporting the profession with legal regulations. While the new profession is only beginning to be introduced in other countries (Unsworth et al., 2024).

Switzerland is facing, like other European countries, challenges in the healthcare system. The situation has been further tightened in the last few years. Swiss healthcare is confronted with a constant shortage of GPs and nurses, over two million multimorbid patients, and an aging society (France Weaver, 2016). Other significant factors are an increase in costs, a shift in demand, and technological advancements. The population is in demand for accessible, high-quality healthcare that is still affordable, despite increasing care needs (Brügger, 2025). These issues have an impact on primary care, particularly on access and care quality at GP practices. The population is concerned about the future of primary healthcare due to the decreasing number of GPs (Reinhard et al., 2024). The profession of APNs is considered an innovative solution to address the challenges and preserve the high quality of healthcare in the country (Zumstein-Shaha, 2022).

1.1.1. International context of the APN role in the healthcare system

APNs are nurses with an advanced degree, enabling a broader scope of practice, additional responsibilities, and working autonomously. APNs follow a holistic approach involving in-depth practice. They have expert knowledge, can deliver complex decision-making skills, and have expanded clinical competencies. Guidelines on APNs are provided globally by the ICN (Schober, 2020).

Role characteristics that differentiate APNs from nurses are education, practice, research, leadership, and professional regulations. Despite their international recognition, these characteristics may vary across different countries due to the current APN integration situation (Schober, 2019). APNs are bachelor-trained nurses who obtain a Master of Science in Nursing or higher education. A specialization in APN roles, such as CNS or NP, can typically be selected at the master's level. Certain countries (e.g., Australia, Canada, and the US) require APNs to complete a predetermined number of hours of clinical practice in order to become a certified APN (Wheeler et al., 2022).

CNS and NP are the two most frequently identified roles in advanced practice nursing. The two roles are capable of operating independently at an advanced level, providing holistic care, and require a minimum of a master's degree (Canadian Nurses Association, 2019). The ICN defines the competencies and scope of practices as follows:

Originally implemented in hospitals, the CNS role has expanded to other settings, such as community care. The scope of practice includes in-depth responsibilities, including direct and indirect care. Direct care addresses direct patient contact, involving families to improve and promote health and quality of life. Indirect care refers to enhancing quality care on a structural level without interaction with patients (Schober, 2020).

NPs are assigned to various settings within the primary healthcare sector. The scope of practice is based on the needs of the population. Thus, NPs' competencies and scope of practice are influenced by the healthcare system and culture of the particular country. In general, NPs offer direct clinical care to patients who are undiagnosed and persistent care to patients who have a diagnosis in outpatient care settings (American Nurses Association, 2021). Within their patient population, they take full responsibility for diagnosis and treatment management. NPs work autonomously and in collaboration with other health

professions. The scope of practice is comprehensive, including diagnosing, advanced health assessments, treatment planning and managing, and prescribing medications and therapeutic interventions. NPs work in interprofessional teams, work evidence-based, and have leadership, education, and research duties within their practice (Schober, 2020).

Both roles are generally observed in their respective environments and operate within the scope of their activities. However, the activities and scope of practice are flexible between the two roles (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Continuum of advanced practice nursing roles. Source: Carter N. Clinical Nurse Specialists and Nurse Practitioners: Title Confusion and Lack of Role Clarity. (Donald et al., 2010).

1.1.2. Swiss context of the APN role in the healthcare system

In Switzerland, the first nursing study program (master diploma) was introduced in 2000 at the University of Basel (Universität Basel, 2023). In 2025, the Master of Science in Nursing program is available in eight universities and universities of applied sciences (only referred to as universities from here on) through the three language areas. As the master's program is not standardized in Switzerland, it varies between the different universities. The program can take between three and six semesters when completed full-time and is awarded with 90, 120, or 180 credit points (ECTs). The universities offer different majors students can specialize in. The majors are "Advanced Practice Nursing" for nursing students who aim to work in a clinical setting and "Research" for nursing students who intend to work in nursing research. As well as extended APN roles at four universities as "Clinical Nurse Specialist", "Nurse Practitioner", and "Psychiatric Mental Health Nurse Practitioner".

The APN roles and study programs in Switzerland are based on Hamric (Tracy et al., 2022). A joint definition for APNs was published in 2013 (swissAPN, 2013). The scope of practice of APNs is in alignment with international roles. However, there is no standardized definition for the two roles of CNSs and NPs, adapted to national regulations and Swiss culture.

The roles of APNs (CNSs) were predominantly integrated into inpatient care due to the national compensation situation. Swiss hospitals use Diagnosis-Related Groups (DRGs). DRGs are funded on a patient's case basis instead of directly by the healthcare provider. That solves the remuneration situation for the new profession in inpatient care. Subsequently, APNs were implemented into care homes and home care (Spitex) (Brügger, 2025). The role of NPs and the implementation of APNs into Swiss primary care started much later. The Université de Lausanne was one of the first universities to offer the major for NPs in 2018. Thus, in the Swiss healthcare system, the role, the scope of practice, and the setting are still developing. This thesis focuses on the implementation of APNs and NPs into Swiss primary care.

The first studies around integrating APNs into Swiss primary care emerged in 2015. Two primary pilot studies involved the integration of APNs into individual GP practices in different cantons. The study from the University of Lucerne integrated four APNs in GP practices in Lucerne, Uri, Schwyz, and Zurich (Sottas et al., 2020) between 2017 and 2020. In this period, the research team supported the APNs and GP practices. Main topics regarding the integration in the practice team, scope of practice, patient feedback, and billing regulation. The second pilot study from the Bern University of Applied Science (BUAS), called “APN in primary care” (Advanced Practice Nurse in der Primärversorgung, PRiMA) (Zumstein-Shaha, 2025). In this pilot study, two APNs were integrated into two GP practices in the canton of Bern from 2020 to 2022. The focus of the study was to evaluate the APN's contribution (self-management, interprofessional teamwork, patient quality of life); assess the billing situation using the TARMED tariff (tariff for outpatient medical services in Switzerland); and develop recommendations for a legal basis and remuneration for APNs in Swiss GP practices. These two pilot studies gave a first understanding of the scope of practice and the dynamics between APNs, the practice team, and patients, and formed a basis for further research.

Even though the national research on APNs/NPs in Swiss primary care increased in the past five years, only little progress was made regarding the implementation of APNs into Swiss primary care. A majority of APNs work in inpatient settings, often specialized in one field with clear responsibilities and tariffs. In a study from 2022, where 497 APNs were asked about their workplace, only twelve (2.4%) APNs stated that they are working in Swiss GP practices (Swiss Nurses Association et al., 2022). This affects patient perspective. In the Swiss Health Observatory (OBSAN) report from 2021, which focuses on the preference of the Swiss population regarding primary healthcare and their providers, only 3.4% of the population would choose an APN as their preferred healthcare provider (Kaufmann et al., 2021). Considering that national studies indicate that APNs improve patient outcomes and that patients who were treated by APNs highly valued the experience (Schönenberger et al., 2020), we suggest that the primary factor influencing the report's preference is a lack of familiarity with the profession.

The challenge with the role understanding and underrepresentation of APNs/NPs in primary care does not end here. As the role is fairly new to healthcare professions, the lack of role understanding is considered a major barrier for successful implementation of APNs/NPs and for finding employment in GP practices (Schober, 2025). National studies have shown that integrating the new profession into an existing practice team is complex. Challenges include unclear competences within the practice team, as there is no standardized scope of practice for APNs/NPs, uncertainties about responsibilities and delegation in patient treatment, and interprofessional communication (Josi et al., 2020; Lauber et al., 2022). One study recommends a mentorship for APNs/NPs starting in GP practices to gain insights into the practice routines and gain confidence and trust from the team (Lauber et al., 2022). Low role recognition is a challenge that cannot be solved solely by APNs/NPs and APN associations. The issue is that the absence of a legal framework and reimbursement for the position is impeding the ability of APNs/NPs to work in primary care.

Currently, there are no legal regulations or frameworks for APNs/NPs who want to work in GP practices. Primary care subjects are legally established by the “Health Professions Act” (Gesundheitsberufegesetz, GesBG) and the “Health Insurance Act” (Krankenversicherungsgesetz, KVG) (Bundesamt für Gesundheit, 1996, 2020). Presently, in the GesBG register, nursing at the master's level is not recognized. Questioning if APNs

are even authorized to work in Swiss primary care. In 2024, a draft amendment to the GesGB was presented, the “Pflegeinitiative” (Nursing Care Initiative). In the draft, the profession of APNs at the master’s level would be recognized as a health profession in the Swiss law GesGB (Bundesamt für Gesundheit, 2025). The consultation on the preliminary draft took place between May and August 2024. During its meeting on May 21st, 2025, the Federal Council approved the proposed draft for the consideration of Parliament. The parliament is now required to decide about the draft (Federal Office of Public Health, 2025).

Moreover, the Swiss Federal Office of Public Health (FOPH) is investigating whether and how APNs will be able to bill for services that align with their expanded competencies in the future on behalf of the Federal Council by the end of 2025 (Federal Office of Public Health, 2025). Currently, APNs are not recognized as health service providers in the KVG, limiting their ability to independently bill for their services. Certain tasks are exclusively performed by physicians (Departement für Gesundheit, Soziales und Kultur, 2019), while others may be completed by other healthcare professionals after a physician has delegated the task. Within these regulations, APNs can only bill for nursing and non-physician tasks in delegation. To enable APNs to bill for themselves, a modification to KVG would be necessary to formally incorporate them into the healthcare provider register (Zumstein-Shaha, 2022).

The nation is still debating this topic, which has yet to be resolved. In the interim, certain cantons establish their own canton-specific regulations. With the implementation of Act 124b, “Infirmiers praticiens spécialisés,” the canton of Vaud became the first to legally authorize APNs as healthcare providers on a cantonal scale in 2017. This regulation facilitates the integration of nursing at the master's level and enables APNs to prescribe and interpret diagnostic tests, perform medical procedures, and prescribe medication (Brügger, 2025). However, the approach is not being implemented on a national scale; only some cantons (including Uri, Glarus, and Geneva) are following it. This could lead to a more ambiguous and non-standardized set of regulations for APNs across Switzerland.

The lack of regulation and legal framework is considered a major barrier for the integration of APNs in Europe and globally (Unsworth et al., 2024). National studies

confirm that the absence of a clear billing regulation is unsettling for APNs as well as for GPs and has a negative impact on role integration (Schober, 2025).

The scope of practice for APNs/NPs in Swiss primary care is limited by the unresolved situation. Except for the canton of Vaud, prescribing medication is a medical task strictly performed by the medical health profession. There is no legal foundation that enables APNs to operate autonomously. Restricting the responsibilities of APNs and hindering the role contribution. Consequently, it is only partially possible to execute their extensive knowledge and full range of practice.

1.2. Objectives

This Ph.D. thesis is about role perception, role definition, and role implementation, which reflects the three projects that were dedicated to the need for research at the current timepoint (Figure 2). The primary objective of the thesis is to contribute to the integration of APNs/NPs into Swiss primary care.

First study

The objective of our first study is to investigate the perspectives and attitudes of the new generation of Swiss APNs toward primary care as a potential future workplace. This research attempts to shift the focus from the needs of the healthcare industry to the perspectives of future APNs, the emerging profession on the matter. We investigated the desire of future APNs, Swiss Master of Nursing students, to work and contribute to primary care, as well as their perceptions of the new role and setting.

Second Study

In our second study, we aim to establish a uniform job description for APNs and NPs in Swiss GP practices. In Switzerland, the role of APNs/NPs in primary care is still not well understood by other healthcare professionals and patients. By defining competencies and proposing a scope of practice, the research intends to facilitate the integration of APNs/NPs into GP practices. Our objective is to enhance the profession's recognition and role in Swiss primary care.

Third study

The third study, conducted in Canada, aims to improve the NP workload measurement tool by assessing acceptability from interest groups. The tool provides a comprehensive overview of NPs' workload and activities in different primary care settings. In order to receive accurate workload data, we evaluate and refine the tool. We want to gain a broader understanding of the activities of NPs in primary care by determining the full workload and potential of NPs.

Figure 2. Focus, research questions, and objectives of the three studies informing this thesis

1.3. Methodology

First study

The first study investigated if master-level nursing students, enrolled at Swiss universities, consider primary care as a potential workplace. At the time (2022), there was no established scope of practice, no billing tariff for APNs who work in primary care, and education programs that focused on NPs were only recently introduced. The study elaborates on the student perspectives, motivations, and attitudes towards the sector as well as the perceived barriers they currently face. Additionally, it evaluated their

willingness to contribute to bridging the primary care gap. We followed a cross-sectional study approach conducted in a Swiss-wide multicenter setting from May to November 2023. Data was selected through a quantitative online survey with an embedded qualitative study part. Statistical analyses and models were performed with R.

We chose the cross-sectional design to obtain a comprehensive and context-specific understanding of the current state. To examine primary facilitators and barriers, the focus is on quantitative data and follows an analytic approach. In addition, the qualitative part of the study gives a deeper comprehension of personal motivation for working in primary care.

Second study

The second study focused on developing a uniform job description for APNs/NPs in primary care, specifically for GP practices. APNs' lack of integration into primary care contributes to the profession's low role recognition. National studies confirmed that in outpatient settings, other healthcare providers as well as patients are unaware of their role and potential, including competencies, field of work, and scope of practice. In collaboration with the BUAS and the APN association APN-CH, we created a uniform job description that outlines the scope of practice for APNs/NPs in GP practices. We used a mixed-methods approach for the study. Data was gathered from literature, sounding board consultations, two focus group discussions, and a validation survey between December 2023 and May 2024. Qualitative data were evaluated using concept mapping; descriptive data were analyzed with R. The results were assembled through in-between triangulation.

We chose a mixed-method approach as the combination of qualitative and quantitative data provided a more profound comprehension of the data and the context. The method enables us to have close cooperation between research and practice and to respond and adapt to ongoing feedback. The in-between triangulation combined the collected results into a single outcome and enhanced the study's validity.

Third study

In our third study, which was conducted in Canada, we were able to examine the workload of integrated NPs with the help of the NP workload measurement tool. The tool was

developed to acquire a more profound understanding of the scope of practice and workload of NPs in various primary care settings. In our study, we investigated the acceptability of the workload measurement tool for NPs among interest groups. The load and distribution of work often remain unclear from an external perspective. We applied a qualitative descriptive study approach. Data were collected through individual semi-structured interviews with NPs and decision-makers who evaluated the tool. Data was gathered from May to July 2024 in Quebec, Canada. Based on the theoretical framework of acceptability, a deductive coding approach was used for the data analysis.

We chose the qualitative approach as it allows the participants to express their experiences and perceptions of the tool in detail in their words. This improves and enriches the quality of the data. The semi-structured interviews grant us to adapt to the participants' answers and opinions while providing consistency and a comparable structure.

The three different approaches were carefully selected for the individual research questions and study designs. In our first study, we would gain a greater understanding of the perspectives of a wide range of future APNs through the collection of quantitative data from nursing students. This information and the results of the study were used to develop and conduct our second study. To acquire a more comprehensive understanding of the current scope of practice in Swiss GP practices, we followed a qualitative data approach. In combination with the quantitative validation of our job description, we were able to confirm our data collected. For our third study, we used a qualitative design to complete the feasibility analysis of the quantitative workload measurement tool for NPs. This approach provided information about how participants viewed the tool and what aspects required adjustment or improvement.

1.4. Key Findings

First study

The first study revealed the overall positive attitude of Swiss APN master students towards the option of working in primary care. Ninety percent of students who obtain an NP major in their studies choose primary care as a potential workplace. The most

significant factors regarding their career choices were *career development* and *job satisfaction*, as assessed by 98% of participants. Linking important factors to primary care, we found a significant positive relation to *community-based working*. The embedded qualitative part gave more profound insights about the reasons for or against working in primary care for the participants. Hereby, the participants stated the positive attitudes are related to “strengthening primary care” and “working autonomously”. The participants who expressed a negative attitude toward primary care stated that they have no “outpatient experience” or are considering the option “later in [their] career.” Most of the participants reported that they think APNs will play a significant role in primary care in the future.

One strength of the study is that 38% of all eligible Master of Nursing students took part in the study, giving a comprehensive overview of the target population. Another strength of the study was the high personal interest in their profession's development, which seems to be a motivation to support research. This was restricted by the limitation of the distribution of the questionnaire at the universities. Five universities sent the survey out via student email; two only permitted the survey to be advertised at the university, reflecting the number of students participating. Another limitation could occur in the form of a response bias, as students who have a higher interest in working in primary care may be more likely to participate in a study on the subject.

The participants' responses indicate that the absence of legal regulations and current obstacles do not affect their perception of the profession's importance or their positive outlook for the future.

Second study

In our second study, we concentrated on the development of a uniform job description for APNs/NPs in Swiss GP practices. A preliminary draft was generated by incorporating eleven existing job descriptions for APNs/NPs in Switzerland. The first draft was discussed by seven sounding board members from different backgrounds, who assisted and accompanied the study team. To enhance this draft, we incorporated the feedback of seven APNs/NPs and five GPs who participated in our focus group discussion. As a last step, the job description draft was validated via an online survey by five of our sounding board members.

The study's significant strength is the close collaboration with professionals and experts from the practice and within the multiprofessional team. Allowing us to directly incorporate the knowledge and experiences of the practice into our research. Another strength of the study is that the uniform job description for APNs/NPs in Swiss GP practices is dedicated specifically to practice and provides the full scope of practice, responsibilities, and activities. Furthermore, non-clinical interest groups will be considered when validating the uniform job description. One limitation of the study is the absence of input from these interest groups.

It can be used as a template that can be adjusted for individual settings and needs. The uniform job description supports the implementation of APNs into Swiss primary care by providing a standard scope of practice, as well as a more profound understanding of the APN role among healthcare professions and patients.

Third Study

The third study, NPs' workload, was documented with the assistance of the NP workload measurement tool. To investigate the tool's acceptability, we conducted interviews with thirteen participants who used the tool for up to four weeks. The participants were questioned regarding the tool's content, clarity, handling, layout and design, and usability, as well as their perception of how well they are represented by it. The tool was perceived as practical and easy to understand and use. The content consists of the relevant tasks and activities completed by NPs in diverse primary care settings. The participants perceived that they were accurately represented and could benefit from the tool to gain a better overview of their daily activities and time management. Minor improvements were suggested by the participants regarding the accessibility of mental health.

A limitation of the study is that the data was collected within one province in Canada and is therefore not to be generalized. Overall, interest groups were supportive of continuing to use the tool and further implementation. A strength of the study is that it provides a valuable perspective on the workload of NPs in primary care.

To investigate the factors that affect the treatment and time management of NPs in various primary care settings, it is necessary to gain a comprehensive understanding of the nature of each patient consultation or administrative task.

1.5. Discussion

Summary

The overall objective of this thesis is to support the integration of APNs/NPs into Swiss primary care and to offer a more profound comprehension of the profession. Role perception, role definition, and role implementation are the subjects of three studies that highlight the complexity of APN/NP integration on multiple levels (Figure 3). Each of the three studies reflects on the need for research at the timepoint in this field and adds new content to the research area. In the following, the key findings, implications, strengths and limitations, and impact of this thesis will be discussed.

Discussing Key Findings

Our first study outcome, which examined APN students' perceptions of primary care as a potential workplace, demonstrates that aspiring APNs/NPs have a favorable opinion of their role in the primary care setting. The overall positive feedback and the willingness to work in primary care in the future align with other national studies (Gysin et al., 2019). With this study, we focused on the personal and individual perspectives of future APNs/NPs instead of the current needs of the healthcare sector (Seematter-Bagnoud et al., 2008). The results of our study indicate that these young professionals are prepared to advocate for primary care, despite the current legal constraints and impediments. Based on the results of the study, the majority of students who participated have a favorable perspective on working in primary care. However, the lack of reimbursement is considered the most negative influencing factor for the students. The findings imply that a defined scope of practice for APNs in primary care is needed, as well as more educational programs for NPs and a national legal framework with a billing tariff. Our results are consistent with the research projects' efforts to facilitate the integration of APNs and NPs into primary care settings (Schlunegger, 2021). Nevertheless, the outcome does not reflect the current work situation of APNs in Switzerland (Swiss Nurses Association et al., 2022). The primary finding of our study and other national studies is that role integration is restricted by the absence of a legal framework and the undefined role of APNs/NPs in primary care (Lauber et al., 2022). National research suggests that

the establishment of a standardized role description for APN/NP in Swiss primary care is necessary to enforce APNs (Schlunegger, 2021).

We addressed the current research and practice needs by developing a uniform job description for APNs in Swiss GP practices. International studies show the significant impact of a clear role definition for a successful integration of APNs into countries (Wheeler et al., 2022). With the uniform job description, we could offer the GPs and their practice team guidance on the tasks, responsibilities, and areas of work associated with the new profession. Studies have observed that one of the most important elements of a successful interprofessional team collaboration is role clarification and a clear role distribution in the practice (Josi et al., 2020; McLaney et al., 2022). In a recent Swiss study, it was stated that the most common barrier to the role performance of APNs is “unclear responsibilities” as a result of an undefined scope of practice (Beckmann et al., 2024). This demonstrates the necessity of guidance in Swiss general practitioner practices and the significance of role clarification for a successful team.

In the context of Canada, where NPs are already integrated healthcare providers, it is important to gain a more profound understanding of NPs work and caseload in primary care (Landry & Kilpatrick, 2024). The study outcome indicates that the workload measurement tool is easy to use and comprehensive. Participants expressed their satisfaction with the visualization and representation of their daily routines. By distinguishing between clinical and non-clinical tasks, a comprehensive overview of their activities can be achieved, thereby facilitating more precise and effective healthcare workforce planning (Kilpatrick et al., 2025). Our study contributed to the improvement of the NP workload measurement tool. How the tool is perceived and adopted by interest groups plays a significant role in the further development of the intervention. International research is frequently used as a role model for Switzerland, which is actively acquiring knowledge to learn from other nations. Validated tools that require only adaptation to national laws are an excellent opportunity to improve and accelerate the process for a sustainable implementation of APNs/NPs into Swiss primary care. National qualitative studies analysing daily practice and activities could profit from the quantitative approach to enhance the data (Altermatt-von Arb et al., 2023).

Table 3. Research focus, objectives, and outcomes in a multi-level framework

Implications

Implications for practice

The uniform job description is the initial practice template, which incorporates the complete scope of practice for APNs/NPs in Swiss GP practices on a national level. The job description is designed to be directly used in practice. As a result, the role and scope of practice of APNs may have a beneficial effect on the integration of APNs into interprofessional teams and the perception of the new profession by the practice team and patients. In additional studies, the job description could be refined by implementing it in a real-world practice setting. To see if the uniform job description has the potential to enhance the recognition and contribute to the implementation of the profession in Swiss GP practices. Furthermore, the integration of the NP workload measurement tool into Swiss primary care settings could give clarification about the actual work and caseload of APNs/NPs working in primary care. With the tool, quantitative data about workload is measured, strengthening the knowledge about NP activities. This data can be used to provide evidence-based workforce planning, cost analysis, and resource allocation. An implementation study that identifies tasks and activities would enhance the scope of practice of Swiss APNs/NPs in this setting. The tool has high potential to contribute to a sustainable implementation of APNs in Swiss primary care.

Implications for politics and regulations

The results of this thesis could help to establish and form a (legal) foundation for the facilitation of APNs/NPs into Swiss primary care. Switzerland's APN politics adhere to a bottom-up approach. Initially, APN education was enabled, and subsequently, it was implemented on a limited scale in primary care. Eventually, legal regulations (Olah, 2025) and national laws will follow. This approach requires strong research, which proves the need of the profession in primary care settings. This research aims to pave the way for national regulations. The “nursing care initiative” (Federal Office of Public Health, 2025), the draft to legally include the profession of APNs into the GeBe, is regarded as a first step for a potential integration of APNs into the KVG as a healthcare provider. This would enable APNs to perform their whole scope of practice and bill for their services, including medicine and nursing tasks. Our studies align with the political approaches as they reflect the perspectives of future APNs as well as define a uniform job description. This could

act as a foundation to define the complete scope of practice that APNs acquire during their education in Switzerland. This thesis supports the necessity of national legal regulations that define the authority and compensation of APNs.

Implications for education and competencies

Our first study implies that 68% of the future APNs/NPs who participated have a favorable perspective on primary care as a potential workplace. Even though there are limited study programs and a not-defined role for APNs in Swiss primary care. International studies have indicated that the interest in the study program increases with an expanded scope of practice (Dankers-de Mari et al., 2023). A combination of a defined scope of practice for APNs/NPs in primary care and more specialization programs could increase the interest of nursing students to work in primary care. Based on our second study, education does not end at the universities. Additionally, mentoring programs could be implemented in the GP practice to enable APNs/NPs to enhance their competencies and acquire practical experience in a secure and supervised environment. Thus, future research could concentrate on a long-term investigation of the actual career transitions of APN/NP students; moreover, a study investigating the initial integration of APNs/NPs into a GP practice and the mentoring they perceive. In addition, further universities are already introducing NP majors, internships at primary care settings, and lectures featuring APNs from different settings.

Strengths and limitations of the Ph.D. thesis

The following attempts to reflect on the strengths and limitations of the Ph.D. thesis, aside from the strengths and limitations of each study. A strength of the thesis is the three different perspectives and methodical approaches in the three studies. The APN situation in Swiss primary care was captured in a distinctive manner by the diversity of researchers from various fields, educations, and specialties, both nationally and internationally. Important insights for our research were derived from the close collaboration with different institutions in all three studies. Limitations of this thesis include legal regulations and the national and international disparities in the profession's implementation.

Impact and prospects

This thesis reflects on different dimensions of the integration of APNs into Swiss primary care. All studies contribute to a more profound understanding of the research area. The thesis forms a valid basis for further research and projects. A long-term study regarding APNs/NPs in Swiss GP practices to test the application of the uniform job description would be an important next step. Furthermore, an economic analysis indicating monetary benefits from APNs/NPs for GP practices would be interesting. Further research could determine the impact of APNs access and treatment for patients in the primary care sector. The implementation of a Swiss-adapted version of the NP workload measurement tool would provide insights about the work and caseload of NPs in different primary care settings.

A supplemental consideration: What can we learn from 65 years of experience with APNs/NPs in the Canadian system?

One of the primary issues facing the Swiss primary care sector is the shortage of personnel (Jörg et al., 2023; Reinhard et al., 2024). The initial APNs in Canada were established 65 years ago as a result of this shortage, particularly in rural areas. Research from Canada shows that APNs can deliver effective and high-quality support in the primary care sector with comparable or better results in terms of hospitalization, health status, and patient satisfaction (Kilpatrick et al., 2024). The Canadian Academy of Health Sciences reported that APNs contribute to and ensure the access and quality of primary care in Canada. The report highlights the alignment of education, legal regulation, and financing to accomplish this integration (Canadian Academy of Health Sciences, 2023). In 2021, in Québec, NPs gained their full practice authority, a legal basis for their whole scope of practice, including nursing and physician activities like prescribing medication (Ordre des infirmières et infirmiers du Québec, 2023). The impact of the collaboration between universities and education for APNs is determined by an additional study from Ontario (Ormiston et al., 2025). Switzerland can profit and learn from Canada's experience in defining clear role competencies, focusing on education, and establishing a legal framework for the new profession.

1.6. Conclusion

APNs can be a part of a sustainable solution to maintain quality and care and support the increasing care demand in Swiss primary care settings. To integrate APNs into this setting, legal regulations, structural-based barriers, and role recognition need to be addressed and solved. Our research findings provide a foundation for potential improvements in this field. Further research can contribute to the advancement of the process and have a substantial impact on the implementation of APNs.

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Chapter 2: Advanced Practice Nurses in Swiss Primary Care—a cross-sectional survey on students' perspectives on primary care as a potential working place.

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